

SOME FEATURES OF AUTOMATIC TOOL CALIBRATION ON CNC MACHINES

FARID MURADOV

Baku Engineering University , Faculty of Engineering, Department of Automation Engineering , 5001 , Khirdalan , Azerbaijan

ANAR MAMMADHUSEYNOV

STP Haevy Engineering LLC , Technical Maintenance department , 5001 , Sumgait , Azerbaijan

Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to investigate the process of automatic calibration of tools (cutting tools) on CNC machines. Automatic calibration determines the length, diameter and location of the tool with high accuracy through sensors and special measuring systems installed on the machine. This information is transmitted to the system, appropriate adjustments are made in the software, and the tool begins the machining process according to real dimensions. As a result, dimensional deviations are reduced, and the accuracy of product processing increases. Unlike manual calibration, this method saves time and prevents human errors. Also, automatic calibration monitors the level of tool wear and ensures timely replacement. This technology plays an important role in increasing productivity, accuracy and technical reliability on CNC machines.*

Keywords: *Composite material; CNC machines, automatic tool adjustment, toolbox, industry 4.0, automatic precision adjustment*

Introduction

stage of development of modern machine-building industry, the development of this branch of heavy industry is a very important base for the development of other industrial facilities, creating an incentive for their general development in the current situation. One of the most promising and effective methods in this direction is the widespread application of various automatic design systems (ALS), automatic machine tools systems (ADS), etc. This approach is more promising for the application of computer tools in the field of mechanical engineering, which ensures the successful development of leading sectors of the economy. The application of computers in mechanical engineering is carried out mainly in two directions : automation of production processes and - automation of engineering labor . The application of Automatic Design Systems to machining is mainly related to the solution of the following problems: a radical reduction in the development time of new equipment and technology , a significant increase in labor productivity, an increase in the reliability of new equipment, a decrease in material and energy consumption , etc. [1-6, 14-16]. Thus, in a modern production environment, high accuracy and rapid production processes require more efficiency from technological equipment. Correct and timely calibration (adjustment) of cutting tools used in CNC (Computer Numerical Control (CNC)) machines is one of the main factors in this regard. The dimensions, location point and wear level of the tools directly affect the processing accuracy. Since traditional calibration (adjustment) methods are time-consuming, dependent on operator experience and open to human errors, the transition to automated solutions in this area has become necessary. Automatic adjustment systems determine the real dimensions of the tool through sensors and measuring devices installed on the machine and transmit this data to the control system. As a result of this process, the software automatically adjusts the operating parameters of the machine. Thus, both the accuracy of the product increases and possible malfunctions during operation are prevented. This article extensively analyzes the technical principles, application methods and industrial significance of automatic adjustment of tools on CNC machines. As a result of the application of automatic adjustment, the level of tool wear can be determined in time, which allows for optimal planning of tool replacement time. At the same time, dimensional deviations arising from adjustment errors are eliminated, product quality is increased,

and production losses are reduced. Automatic recording and archiving of adjustment data simplifies quality control processes and contributes to the development of digital manufacturing systems within the framework of Industry 4.0 [7-9, 11-13]. Figure 1 shows the automatic tool change in CNC machines. The calibration system (often called a "probe calibration system" or "tool setter calibration kit") used for calibration (adjustment) and checking measurement accuracy is shown [10].

Figure 1. Automatic **calibration of instruments** Calibration system used for (adjustment) and checking measurement accuracy

Now let's explain the function of the numbered parts in the picture: Explanation of the elements in the picture:

- **Calibration probe (Tool Probe / Touch Probe):**

This part is placed on the main rotating tool holder (spindle) of the machine tool. The spherical part (touch ball) at the end allows you to measure coordinates by contacting the spindle. The software determines the position and size of the tool based on these contact points

- **Calibration Block / Master Block:**

The main reference surface used for calibration. The precise contact of the sample with this surface allows the system to determine its "zero point" coordinates.

- **Calibration Bar:**

A reference bar of fixed length used to check the measurement range of a sample and in the calibration process. The dimensions of this bar correspond to precise standards.

- **Mounting Shaft:**

Used to secure the reference block or rod to the machine bed or table. Important for stable and vibration-free measurement.

- **Base Plate:**

Provides a stable, flat surface for mounting the reference block and other parts. It is important for calibration accuracy that the surface is perfectly flat and stable.

- **Mounting Bolts & Clamps:**

Used to secure the entire system to the machine. It is important to ensure that the elements do not move, otherwise the calibration results may be incorrect.

2. Section

Accurate determination of tool length in CNC machines is one of the factors that directly affects the accuracy of the machine and the quality of the product. In traditional methods, these measurements were performed manually by the operator, which was open to human errors, as well as causing time loss and calibration errors. To overcome these shortcomings, tool length measurement sensors - tool setters - are widely used in modern CNC systems. Tool setters are high-precision sensors that automatically determine the length of the tool by sending a signal when it comes into contact with the tip. The structure of these devices usually includes a contact disk, a pneumatic cleaning system and a signal transmission mechanism. After the tool is changed, the system measures the distance between the tip of the new tool and the sensor and enters this

information into the CNC program. Thus, a separate and accurate compensation value is determined for each tool. The main parts of the device include the following:

1. **Contact disc (top gold cap)** : Contact is made when the tool touches this surface.
2. **Housing** : Metal housing for mechanical stability and sensor protection.
3. **Pneumatic input** : Air pressure connection for cleaning and automatic resetting of the device (blue port in figure 2).
4. **Cable or pipe passage** : For connecting the sensor to the CNC control system. Thanks to this system , the calibration process during tool changes is automated , errors during operation are reduced , and the machine operates with maximum accuracy with minimum downtime . Automatic calibration of instruments and sensor diagnostics are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. **Automatic calibration of instruments, sensor** diagnostics

The device depicted in Figure 2 is a "Tool Setter" used for automatic measurement of tool length in CNC machine tools . This device allows the machine tool to automatically measure the length of the new tool after the tool change process and transmit it to the control system. The device shown in the figure is an automatic tool length measurement sensor (Tool Length Setter) used in CNC machine tools. These sensors generate a signal when they come into contact with the tool tip, determine the real length , and transmit this information to the CNC system. Thus, the need for manual measurement by the operator is eliminated and measurement accuracy is increased . Thanks to this technology, operator intervention is minimized, time loss is reduced, machine productivity is increased, and measurement stability is ensured. Tool length sensors act as one of the main components of automatic calibration and play an indispensable role in modern manufacturing processes. As a result, the integration of automatic calibration systems into CNC machine tools acts as one of the main components of technological progress in modern manufacturing processes. This technology not only increases the competitiveness of manufacturing enterprises, but also significantly increases labor productivity and production accuracy. The calibration and operating parameters of tools on a CNC lathe are described in table 1.

Table 1. Calibration **and operating parameters of CNC tools**

No.	Tool name	Cutting speed (m/min)	Operating temperature (°C)
1.	<i>End mill</i>	180	45
2.	<i>Spiral drilling</i>	150	40
3.	<i>Internal spiral</i>	120	60

	<i>drilling</i>		
4.	<i>External turning tool</i>	150	55
5.	<i>Internal turning tool</i>	200	58

● **Cutting speed (m/min):** The rotational/feed speed of the tool at the moment it is in contact with the workpiece.

● **Operating temperature (°C):** The temperature of the tool measured during operation. Excessive heat increases the risk of wear.

● **Calibration type:** The method by which the length or coordinates of the instrument are determined.

● **Automatic monitoring:** Continuous monitoring of the tool by sensors during operation (yes, no).

● **Dimensional deviation:** The difference between the actual dimensions of an instrument after calibration and the intended dimensions.

CNC lathe The actual working process of a cutting tool on a machine tool is shown in Figure 3 [6].

Figure 3. View of the real working process of a cutting tool on a CNC lathe

The CNC lathe, as shown in Figure 3, is used to process rotating parts with high precision. However, to ensure this accuracy, it is important to center the part and position the tool precisely. For this purpose, the calibration of the tools and the chuck is of particular importance. The part is clamped using a three-jaw chuck. If the clamping center of the chuck is not calibrated or has an axial runout, no matter how accurate the tool is, errors will occur during machining. For this reason, the calibration of the chuck and the axis must be checked regularly and must comply with standards [6]. In addition, the cutting tool in the figure performs a shaping operation by touching the part. The length, radial position and zero point of this tool must be determined in advance by the machine using calibration sensors or probe systems. If the calibration is not performed correctly, this will lead to dimensional deviations, surface defects and premature wear of the tool.

1. **Part runout** - Maximum permissible axial deviation: $\leq 0.005 \text{ mm}$
2. **Tool length accuracy** - Actual length difference measured by automatic tool setter: $\pm 0.01 \text{ mm}$
3. **Tool tip radius tolerance:** $\pm 0.005 \text{ mm}$
4. **Chuck clamping force** - Part clamping force: **2–5 kN (varies by model)**
5. **Spindle RPM** - Recommended during calibration: **0–100 RPM** (low speed during contact measurement)

6. Automatic compensation system - a system that automatically applies the measurement difference after calibration (ON/OFF)

7. Instrument adjustment time - Automatic calibration time: **10–30 seconds** (depending on instrument and system)

8. Calibration probe sensitivity - Sensor signal response accuracy: **0.001 mm or less**

9. Workpiece temperature - Before measurement: **20–23°C** (measurement accuracy increases at a constant temperature)

3. Conclusions

Correct and accurate calibration is essential for high-quality and accurate operation of tools on CNC machines. Timely and regular tool calibration minimizes measurement errors, increases accuracy and product quality in the production process. Keeping the technical parameters obtained as a result of calibration under control increases the service life of the equipment and reduces the risk of accidents. At the same time, calibration documentation and compliance with standards ensure the competitiveness of production at the international level by meeting the requirements of industry standards. In the future, the application of automated systems and digital technologies in the calibration process will further increase the accuracy and efficiency of calibration. In general, tool calibration is one of the main factors ensuring the stability and productivity of production systems.

LITERATURE

1. Amirov F. Developing Criterion and optimization of PAL system. Applied mechanics and materials. 2013 Nov 14;379:244-9.
2. Abbasov V, Amirov F, Amirli S, Hasanli S, Frana K. Formation of Shaft Accuracy during Mechanical Processing on CNC Machines. Advances in Science and Technology. 2024 Jun 3;148:81-6.
3. Amirov FG. General provisions of creating adjustable automatic machine systems. Assembly in machine building, instrumentation. 2011(7):44-8.
4. Bashirov RJ, Amirov FG. Method for determining the thermal state of the cylinder sleeve during centrifugal induction sintering. Izvestiya vysshikh uchebnykh zavedeniy. Machinostroenie. 2022:33-41.
5. Bashirov RJ, Amirov FG. Method for determining the thermal state of the cylinder sleeve during centrifugal induction sintering. Izvestiya vysshikh uchebnykh zavedeniy. Machinostroenie. 2022:33-41.
6. Amirov FG. Classification of details by size, method of construction of coordinate system details for geometric modeling. News of higher educational institutions. Machine building. 2012(8):32-5.
7. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Research of the Dependence of Microhardness on Cutting Modes during Waterjet Treatment of Hardox-500 Chrome-Nickel Steel. Herald of Azerbaijan Engineering Academy. 2024 Dec 30;16(4):27-33.
8. Amirov FG. Some features of increasing the productivity of automatic lines. News of higher educational institutions. Machine building. 2020(9 (726)):18-23.
9. Amirov FG. Optimization of planning decisions of automated machine tool systems. Progressive technologies and machine building systems. 2011(42):11.
10. Simon S, Yusubov N, Amirli S, Amirov F. Planning of Full Factorial Experiments for the Investigation of Roughness in Hydroabrasive Waterjet Cutting of Hardox-500 Steel. Pakistan Journal of Life & Social Sciences. 2024 Jul 1;22(2).
11. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Waterjet cutting of HARDOX-500 workpiece. Russian Engineering Research. 2024 Nov;44(11):1572-6.
12. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Surface Roughness of Chromonickel Steel after Water Jet Machining: A Full Factorial Experiment. Russian Engineering Research. 2025 Mar;45(3):341-5.

13. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Research of the Dependence of Microhardness on Cutting Modes during Waterjet Treatment of Hardox-500 Chrome-Nickel Steel. Herald of Azerbaijan Engineering Academy. 2024 Dec 30;16(4):27-33.
14. Fraña K, Neubert C, Simon S, Mammadov A, Amirov F. A Flow Study in the Cyclone with Particle Separations. In International Conference on Computational & Experimental Engineering and Sciences 2020 Dec 15 (pp. 52-59). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
15. Amirov FG. Unification of instrumental units in the position of mechanical processing of alloys with directional crystallization of eutecnic structures on multi-stream automatic lines. Vestnik mashinostroeniya. 2020 Oct(10):79-81.
16. Amirov FG. Some aspects of increasing the efficiency of automated production lines. Izvestiya vysshih uchebnyh zavedeniy. Mashinostroenie. Bauman Moscow State Technical University. (Moscow). 2020;9:18-23.
17. Fariz Amirov G, Ilgar Shiraliyev T. Research on wear and tear of the mud pump liners.
18. Amirov F. Die Klassifizierung von Bauteilen für regulier-bzw. einrichtbaren automaticen Fertigungslinien unter Verwendung von CNC Werkzeugmaschinen. Energieeffizienz im Bau- und Maschinenwesen. 2017:7.
19. Amirov FG. Features of the concentration of instrument blocks in the position of mechanical processing on multi-flow automatic lines. Izvestiya Azerbaijan National Aerospace Agency. 2014;17(1):27.
20. Amirov FG. Distinctive features of machining operation at positions. Vestnik mashinostroyeniya. 2013(1):49-51.
21. Amirov FG. Features of mechanical processing on positions. Herald of machine building. 2013(1):49-51.
22. Amirov F. Pre-project analysis of production. Herald of machine building. 2012(2):75-9.
23. Amirov FG. Pre-project analysis of production in automated machine tool systems. Mechanics of mechanical engineering. 2011(2):123.
24. Amirov FG. Features of combining instrument blocks in the position of mechanical processing on automatic lines. Scientific works. 2012(1):26.
25. Amirov FG. "Technological processes of multi-nomenclature large-scale production". I International scientific conference "Nanotechnology and their application in technology": December 15-16. In 1-я Междунар. науч. conf." Nanotechnologies and application of them in technology". Baku 2010 (p. 210).
26. Dzhanakmedov AH, Amirov FG. STATUS AND PERSPECTIVES OF IS - USE OF NON-TRADITIONAL RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES. Assembly in machine building, instrumentation. 2009(10):51-5.
27. Amirov FG. Increasing the efficiency and ensuring the reliability of automatic lines. Herald of machine building. 2004(5):77-8.
28. Amirov FG. Ways to improve the efficiency of aggregate machines and automatic lines. Mechanical engineering. 2002(2):35.
29. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Surface Roughness of Chromonickel Steel after Water Jet Machining: A Full Factorial Experiment. Russian Engineering Research. 2025 Mar;45(3):341-5.
30. Amirov FG, Shiraliyev IT. External Wear of a Flush Pipe in a Drilling Rig. Russian Engineering Research. 2025 May;45(5):629-34.
31. Simon S, Yusubov N, Amirli S, Amirov F. Research on Some Issues of the Processed Surface Formation in the Hydroabrasive Cutting of Chrome-Nickel Steels. In International Symposium on Unmanned Systems and the Defense Industry 2024 May 22 (pp. 275-281). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
32. Abbasov V, Amirov F, Karimov A. Features of the New Design of the Camshaft of Internal Combustion Engines. In International Symposium on Unmanned Systems and the Defense Industry 2024 May 22 (pp. 282-288). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

33. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Research of the Dependence of Microhardness on Cutting Modes during Waterjet Treatment of Hardox-500 Chrome-Nickel Steel. Herald of Azerbaijan Engineering Academy. 2024 Dec 30;16(4):27-33.
34. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Some features of chip formation during hydroabrasive processing. News of higher educational institutions. Machine building. 2024(11 (776)):53-61.
35. Simon S, Yusubov ND, Amirli SF, Amirov FG. Some features of chip formation during hydroabrasive processing. News of higher educational institutions. Machine building. 2024(11 (776)):53-61.
36. Amirli SF, Fritsche P, Abbasov IT, Wichmann S, Simon S, Amirov FG, Mammadov AS. The impact of high speed mechanical processing efficiency on the production process. Herald of Azerbaijan Engineering Academy. 2022 Mar 30;14(1):41-51.
37. Amirov FG. Uniting of instrument blocks in the position of mechanical processing of alloys with directed crystallization of eutectic structures on multi-flow automatic lines. Herald of machine building. 2020(10):79-81.
38. Sultan-Zade NM, Amirov FG. Разработка процесса процесса оптимизации технологических процессх для ПАЛ. News of higher educational institutions. Machine building. 2013(7):66-72.
39. Amirov FG. Structural layouts of adjustable automatic lines for details such as wire rotation. Herald of machine building. 2012(3):85-6.
40. Amirov FG. Increasing the efficiency of automatic lines with flexible connection due to transport-accumulation systems of the dead-end type.